

Transparent Filler: Enhancing LUE in thick-film Semitransparent Organic Solar Cells

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Abstract

Organic solar cells (OSCs) have attracted significant interest due to their low cost, flexibility, solution processability and semitransparency. In particular, semitransparent OSCs are promising for building-integrated and agricultural applications. However, up-scaling production requires a thicker photoactive layer to minimize defects, which typically compromises the transparency and sometimes even the power conversion efficiency (PCE), thereby leading to a reduction in light utilization efficiency (LUE).

To address this challenge, we introduced PS as transparent filler into blade-coated PTQ10 based solar cells to increase the thickness and transparency, as illustrated in the figure below. We investigated the influence of different content of PS on device performance and found that the addition of PS into the photoactive layer induces phase separation and the degree of phase separation increases with the increasing PS amount, resulting in a reduced device performance. Nevertheless, incorporating PS enhances the transparency of the OSC and shifts the optimal PCE towards larger active layer thickness, achieving an improvement of

the LUE of thick-film semitransparent OSCs. Finally, with silver nanowires blade-coated as the transparent top electrode, a LUE above 2.4% was achieved with a 200 nm thick PTQ10 based photoactive layer. Our work demonstrates that transparent fillers are a viable approach to facilitate future scalable fabrication of high-performance semitransparent OSCs.

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Figure: Schematic illustration for Transparent Filler concept.